

**FEATURES OF POSTMODERNISM IN “TIME’S ARROW”
BY MARTIS AMIS.**

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This article investigates the important features of postmodernism in Martin Amis’s novel “Time’s Arrow”. Through its structure, post modernistic features, such as, fragmented identity, and ironic approach to historical events, the novel includes conventional storytelling and involves postmodernist concerns such as the instability of truth, the deconstruction of time, and the unreliability of viewpoint. By examining how these elements are used in the text, this study highlights the ways in which Amis joins direct connection and traditional notions of character and action. Ultimately, “Time’s Arrow” exemplifies the postmodern visual, reflecting a fragmented and ironic worldview that attracts readers to rethink about the destructive world described in the novel.

INTRODUCTION. The article reveals the importance of employing original concepts, different tones, as well as in-depth subject discussions that forms the essence of Amis’ affirmative impact to extended current Britain’s literature text. Some of the novels include; “Money”, “London Fields” and “Time’s Arrow” most of the works of Martin Amis involve themes of morality, identity and grotesque aspect of life. His novel “Time’s Arrow” has not only a rather unconventional and unusual structure but also merely audacious approach to the issues of history, consciousness, and time.

Postmodernism is a literary movement that took root in mid twentieth century as a reaction to modernism movement. It undermines grand concepts and absolute truths, does not tell a story in a clear, linear manner and such methods as irony, style intertwinement,

and allusions. The postmodern books may depict fiction and reality, and when they are narrated they twist the mind of the readers challenging what the reader has in mind about a particular story.

“Time’s Arrow” has many elements of postmodernism due to its unconventional plot and its concentration on metaphysical questions concerning historical time. Telling the story, Amis breaks conventional rules governing story-telling and forces readers to think in new directions about cause and effect, right and wrong, and the self’s construction. This paper examines how the reversed timeline of the novel and its main character’s fragmented identity, as well as its postmodernist approach to history sitcoms, are postmodern. It also shows that Martin Amis contributes to the development of the postmodern style and relates to its greater concerns.

Literature Review

This work by Martin Amis has been the cause of many discussions since it was written. Because the themes covered in it show the main characteristics of postmodernism. His work has been discussed by many writers and critics. Scholars have recognized the novel as a significant example of how postmodernism engages with history, ethics, and the nature of human consciousness.

The chronology in “Time’s Arrow” is often cited as an essential postmodern mood. According to Hutcheon, this work is a work created by a writer who avoids simplicity and has a unique approach to contemporary events. These are the views of the writer who expressed his opinion and opposition to the changes in the world.²⁸ Richardson emphasizes how the events in the novel makes readers think about history in unusual ways²⁹. The timeline in the novel isolates the reader, creating a distancing effect that calls ethical and philosophical reflection, a key aspect of postmodernist literature.

Moreover, Waugh states that postmodernism period frequently involves history through ironical strategies that Amis uses to criticize and reinterpret historical events³⁰. In “Time’s Arrow”, this is obvious from the protagonist’s observation about the actions happening around.

²⁸ Currie, M. (2013). “About Time: Narrative, Fiction, and the Philosophy of Time.” Edinburgh University Press.

²⁹ Richardson, B. (2006). “Unnatural Voices: Extreme Narration in Modern and Contemporary Fiction.” Ohio State University Press.

³⁰ Waugh, P. (1984). “Metafiction: The Theory and Practice of Self-Conscious Fiction.” Routledge.

Morrison³¹ says that the opinion of the main character in "Times Arrow" about world events makes the reader think more, and under the influence of these events, the reader makes a deep reflection on world events.

According to McHale³², works written in the spirit of postmodernism include psychological and literary features. Because of this, he emphasizes that this work is distinguished from other works by its deep reflection of the human psyche.

METHODOLOGY

In carrying out this research, we have used textual analysis. In addition, before finding the elements of postmodernism reflected in the work, the characteristics of this period have been studied. We have found such elements and features in the work and analyzed them. Postmodernism, as its name implies, has a high probability of influencing human emotions and psyche of the events taking place in the modern world. Because of this, there are many such elements in the work, which have been analyzed and revealed in the article. By deeply analyzing the novel's structure, themes, and stylistic elements, the research has been concluded about what postmodernist themes and structures have been used to create this novel.

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

Martin Amis's "Time's Arrow" is a novel that includes postmodernist features through its unique style and structure, historical events, and the explanation of isolated identity. In this part of the article, extracts from the work "Times Arrow" that reflect the main characteristics and elements of postmodernism are analyzed. For example: "*I sensed their vigor, scarcely held in check, like the profusion of their body hair; and the forbidding touch of their forbidding hands—doctor's hands, so strong, so clean, so aromatic. Although my paralysis was pretty well complete, I did find that I could move my eyes. At any rate, my eyes moved. The doctors seemed to be availing themselves of my immobility. They were, I sensed, discussing my case, but also other matters having to do with their copious free time: hobbies, and so on. And the thought came to me, surprising in its fluency and confidence, fully formed, fully settled: How I hate doctors. Any doctors. All doctors...*"³³.

Analysis. One of the main characteristics of postmodernism is that the events happening in a person's mind do not correspond to the surrounding events at all. This means that the feelings that the hero feels in the passage and the conversation or actions of the people

³¹ Morrison, J. (2007). "Contemporary Fiction." Routledge.

³² McHale, B. (1987). "Postmodernist Fiction." Routledge

³³ Amis, Martin. *Time's Arrow*. Vintage International, 1991. P.-1;

around him are completely contradictory. In this case, readers are forced to think a little more deeply about what is happening. In most cases, the opinion of the hero and the students may not agree with each other. This is also a feature of the postmodernist theme.

“As life speeds up like this I move among the urban people, in the urban setting, the city's metal and mortar, its sharper interactions, with more grit and bite in the gears.”³⁴ Through this passage we can learn that another characteristic of postmodernism is the rapid passage of time, the use of expressions that indicate its non-stop. In postmodernism, time is a fleeting life, nothing is eternal. It points to the fact that everything is transitory.

“You don't see cyclists wearing those doctor's masks. There are no more warnings, on pollen days, for asthmatics and hay-fever sufferers. Everyone smokes and drinks and messes around. No one works out.”³⁵

Analysis. Through the statement “No one works out”, the writer points to the indifference of people to their health in the modern world, and the weakening of attention to health. In addition, we can witness the names of diseases in this passage. He even emphasized the absence of warnings for sick people. The thoughts that people drink and smoke because they do not value their health so much can be considered as the result of “neglect” which is a feature of postmodernism.

“The city—it is the city that will have to heal them, with knife blade and automobile, nightstick, gunshot. The local passions of love and hate. The loose cables and rogue masonry of the telekinetic city.” We can see that this description characterizes the postmodern city. Phrases such as “loose cables” and “rogue masonry” indicate that the city is completely falling apart, that the structures in it are not working properly, that everything is out of order. From this we can understand that the life of the city and the life of people have started to go completely out of track and it seems that everything and people do not understand their duties and responsibilities. The development of urbanization serves to further reveal the characteristics of postmodernism.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, we can say that “Times Arrow” by Martin Amis is one of the most important works of the postmodern era. Through this research, we have studied the main features of postmodernism. In addition, we got acquainted with the opinions of scientists and critics who worked in this direction on postmodernism. Since the article is focused on

³⁴ Amis, Martin. *Time's Arrow*. Vintage International, 1991. P.-2;

³⁵ The same novel: P.-41;

the analysis of the work, using the method of textual analysis, we found and analyzed the fragments in the work "Times Arrow" that included elements of postmodernism. It can be concluded from this that postmodernism is a period that expresses the neglect of people's lives due to the intensification of city life, does not appreciate time, even if it flows like water, and does not recognize the habits that cause life to go off track. . Through these thoughts, the writer tried to reveal how the events happening in the modern world are destroying humanity through this work.

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